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Title: “Creating that safe space is vital”: perspectives of stakeholders involved in the implementation of a mobile Health Bus intervention for Gypsy, Roma and Traveller communities

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Introduction: Gypsy Roma and Traveller Communities (GRTC) experience lower life expectancy and poor physical and psychological health, driven by poverty, deprivation, unemployment and limited engagement with health services. GRTC communities face barriers when accessing healthcare, which often lead to presenting late to services and reduced opportunities for early support and assistance. This study evaluates the value of a mobile Health Bus intervention which was commissioned by Rotherham Doncaster and South Humber NHS Foundation Trust to provide regular visits to GRTC sites across Doncaster.

Methods: Semi-structured one-to-one interviews were conducted with six stakeholders regarded as service implementors. Thematic analysis was used to explore research questions related to understanding the value of the Health Bus intervention and determine future service and policy recommendations. Themes are presented in *Italics* in the next section.

Results: The Health Bus was reported as a flexible resource for facilitating engagement with GRTC. There was a strong sense that the Health Bus provided an informed approach to support healthcare choice, achieved by *building cultural competency and awareness* with stakeholders. Mutual respect and trust could facilitate more effective communication in tackling *contextual and systemic challenges*. This environment should allow better *accessibility of service delivery* and importantly: *navigating, rather than signposting* to appropriate healthcare services.

Conclusions: The Health Bus provided an important mechanism to engage GRTC in Doncaster. Stakeholders regarded the Health Bus as an opportunity to develop a “safe space” and to potentially empower GRTC to be able to navigate healthcare support systems as well as providing regular access.